

**INFLUENCE OF THE COOLING RATE ON THE ADHESIVE PROPERTIES OF
POLYAMID-6-GALVANIZED-STEEL-HYBRIDS IN A ONE-STEP FORMING PROCESS**T.Fischer¹, W. Hua², H. Palkowski³ and G. Ziegmann⁴¹Tobias Fischer, Centre of Material Technology, Agricolastraße 2,
Clausthal-Zellerfeld, Germany, tobias.fischer@tu-clausthal.de, www.czm.tu-clausthal.de²Wei Hua, Institute of Metallurgy, Robert-Koch-Straße 42,
Clausthal-Zellerfeld, Germany, wei.hua@tu-clausthal.de, www.imet.tu-clausthal.de³Prof. Dr.-Ing. Heinz Palkowski, Institute of Metallurgy, Robert-Koch-Straße 42,
Clausthal-Zellerfeld, Germany, heinz.palkowski@tu-clausthal.de, www.imet.tu-clausthal.de
Prof. Dr.-Ing. Gerhard Ziegmann, Institute of Polymer Materials and Plastics Engineering, Agricolastraße 6, Clausthal-Zellerfeld, Germany, Ziegmann@puk.tu-clausthal.de, www.puk.tu-clausthal.de**Keywords:** One-step forming, Crystallinity, Composite, Metal/Polyamide, Hybrid material**ABSTRACT**

The production of sandwich structures as combinations of polymers and metals increased strongly in the past years and different ways have been established to produce them. The focus of this work is the production in a one-step variothermal pressing process and in this context the influence of the cooling rate on the bonding quality of the mono-materials. The investigated manufacturing process has the special feature that the temperature control of the tool is operated by two oil cycles, one for heating and one for cooling the system. The influence of the cold circuit temperature was investigated in detail as well as its effect on the crystallinity and the bonding of the mono-materials. For this purpose, four-point bending tests as well as lap shear tests and microscopic analyses were carried out.

1 INTRODUCTION

Benefits such as higher stiffness, weight reduction and better damping behavior of new hybrid materials by combining the advantages of the mono-materials are well known nowadays [1]. In the course of the past decades, this knowledge led to a wide variety of different applications for hybrid materials. The materials combinations ranged from application fields in the automotive sector up to high-tech materials for aircraft as well as mechanical engineering. For the production of metal/thermoplastic polymer (with or without fiber-reinforcement)/metal structures several ways are established. The production can be done via different researched processes like wet compression molding, variothermal forming or coating techniques [2, 3]. The process used in this publication is the one-step variothermal forming. On the one hand, this process requires less process steps than conventional methods and on the other hand, resources and process time can be reduced. One of the critical points of this manufacturing process is the temperature control of the forming tool and the resulting temperature profile within the raw material during the heating and cooling phases. While heating does not have a significant influence on the materials behavior of the sandwich structure, as long as the thermal stress of the polymer allows this, cooling has a significant impact. The subject of this publication is to investigate the impact of different cooling temperature profiles focusing on the mechanical properties of the resulting products. Additionally the focus of the analyses is the extended view on the relation between the different cooling rates and the resulting crystallinities [4, 5].

2 HYBRID FORMING PROCESS

The forming of the metal/polymer/metal sandwich structure and thus the production of the samples takes place in a modified deep-drawing press, which is equipped with a variothermal 2-cycle temperature control unit. The raw materials used are pre dried polyamide 6, adhesive agent and tempered galvanized steel. As shown in Figure 1, a U-section is chosen as the geometry for first investigations. It allows the general manufacturing process to be investigated, such as temperature, layer structure or pressure. At the same time, the section demonstrates the first characteristic step of the mechanical

properties of the thermoforming deep drawing process. For this purpose, it was divided into different areas implying different challenges in production. In the first step, the punch surface was examined to investigate the effects of different crystallinities shown in Figure 1 (a). A short preheating in the forming tool and subsequent forming and cooling of the component was carried out for preparation of the laminate sheets.

Figure 1: Finite element simulation of the polyamide-6-glvanized-steel-hybrid

Special attention was given to the temperature control unit, which has two separate oil cycles for heating and cooling. Since the cold oil reaches the heated mould at the beginning of the cooling process, a deep temperature gradient occurs which decreases over time due to the heat transfer. Due to the cooling down of the mould, a varying cooling rate is obtained during the process of cooling as can be seen in Figure 2. A sensor located in the flank of the section records the temperature.

Figure 2: Exemplary heating and cooling process

2.1 Experimental setup

There are two different experimental setups with different core layers. One for a foil of polyamide 6 with a thickness of 0.5 mm, later described as polyamide. The other setup for a glass fibre-reinforced pre-impregnated polyamide 6 foil with a thickness of 0.5 mm and a twill 2/2 of fibreglass fabric with an area weight of 600 g/m² and a fibre content of 47 vol.-%, later described as organosheet. The core layer is placed between two galvanised metal sheets (TS 275) with a thickness of 0.4 mm each as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Schematic layer structure with a core material of organosheet

To prepare the layers for the forming process, the metal sheet is mechanically treated using SiC grinding paper with a grain size of 60, aiming to achieve more mechanical interlocking of the polymer and metallic sheet, then cleaned with isopropanol and tempered for one minute at 440 ° to remove contaminations from the surface. Additionally, this creates a uniform and defined zinc oxide layer for all samples. After this pre-treatment the adhesive agent based on an aminoterminated copolyamide consisting of polyamide-12 was applied and activated at 250 °C for 3 min. for further cross-linking. The core layer is placed between the metallic sheets and transferred to the preheated variothermal press at a mould temperature of 220 °C, held for 1 min. and cooled at various cooling circuit temperatures as shown in Table 1. Spacer plates with a thickness of 1.3 mm are used for the samples without fibre-reinforcement to produce a uniform layer thickness and avoid uncontrolled squeezing out of the polymer in melted state. For the fiberglass-reinforced samples, spacer plates were not used. The press force was set to 120 kN with a punching speed of 7 mm/s. With a sample area of 320 mm x 60 mm, this corresponds to a contact pressure of 6.25 N/mm². The press force was maintained until 105 °C is reached (except in tests 6&13) the samples were demoulded at a temperature of 85 °C. The temperature of the hot cycle was maintained at 260 °C in all experiments. In order to determine the standard deviation, three tests were carried out at the standard cooling cycle temperature of 80 °C in each case. Afterwards, experiments with an increased cooling cycle temperature of 100 °C, experiments with a decreased cooling cycle temperature of 50 °C and tests without cooling were carried out. In the tests with the polyamide foil an additional experiment with cooling of the hot circuit was carried out which also led to a significantly lower cooling rate than the direct switching to the cold cycle.

Number	Sample	Tool temperature hot cycle in °C	Tool temperature cold cycle in °C	Demolding temperature in °C	Time to demolding in min.
1	Organosheet	220	80	85	8.9
2	Organosheet	220	80	85	9.1
3	Organosheet	220	80	85	9.2
4	Organosheet	220	100	100	9.5
5	Organosheet	220	50	85	5.1
6	Organosheet	220	1*	-	59.5 (until 85°C)
7	Polyamide	220	80	85	9.1
8	Polyamide	220	80	85	9.2
9	Polyamide	220	80	85	9.0
10	Polyamide	220	2*	85	15.9
11	Polyamide	220	100	100	8.2
12	Polyamide	220	50	85	5.3
13	Polyamide	220	1*	-	58.4 (until 85°C)

1* No active cooling, 2* Cooling of the hot cycle

Table 1: Experiments, overview

2.2 Sample preparation

To characterize the samples, which were taken from the bottom area of the U-section (Figure 1), two test methods were selected. On the one hand the adhesion between the core layer and the surface layer is investigated by lap shear tests. On the other hand influences of a change in crystallinity on the bending properties of the composite is investigated by four-point bending. The samples were cut as shown in Figure 4. The lap shear tests were performed with an initial force of 10 N and a test speed of 1 mm/min. Due to the low surface layer thickness, the tests had to be carried out with a reduced overlapping area of 5 mm x 25 mm. The four-point bending tests based on DIN EN ISO 14125 with a sample size of 15 mm x 25 mm. Test conditions are an initial force of 5 N, a test speed of 1 mm/min and a span of 21,45 mm. Samples were cut to size using an impact shear.

Figure 4: Sample preparation

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In order to investigate the influences of the cooling speed and consequently the cooling rate on the process, the temperature and cooling rates were investigated. Additionally, differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) measurements were carried out at defined cooling rates. Afterwards, mechanical tests are carried out and examined by microscopic observation.

3.1 Differential scanning calorimetry

In order to investigate the degree of crystallinity during the experiments, reference measurements with fixed cooling rates were performed in the DSC. A range from 2 K/min up to 45 K/min was investigated as to be seen in Figure 5. A nearly linear dependency of the crystallinity on the cooling rate of the polyamide samples could be observed. The situation is rather different for samples made of fiber-reinforced polyamide. However, a similar process is to be recognized. It is also noticeable that the fiber-reinforcement indicates a nucleating influence leading to a higher crystallinity. An explanation for the increased fluctuation can be traced back to the nominal fiber volume content. Since even small changes in the fiber volume content and thus in the polymer content has a high effect on the calculation of crystallinity.

Considering the recrystallization temperatures of the two materials obtained from the DSC measurement as well, a trend can be observed which is useful for later evaluations of the crystallinity shown in Figure 6 and Figure 7. A shifting of the recrystallization temperature occurs. This phenomenon has been observed in other plastics as well [6]. A possible explanation could be thermodynamic effects. With these results the recrystallization temperature as a function of the cooling rate can be determined. In connection with the dependence of the crystallinity on the cooling rate shown in Figure 5, an iterative estimation of the crystallinity of the polyamide is carried out, further described as theoretical crystallinity.

Figure 5: DSC measurements with fixed cooling rates for the polyamide 6 film and the organosheet

Figure 6: Recrystallization of the polyamide

Figure 7: Recrystallization of the organosheet

Measuring the crystallinity of the manufactured specimens is more complex compared to previous tests of the unprocessed materials of the core layer. On the one hand, the change of the fibre volume content of the samples made of glass fibre-reinforced polyamide has an effect on the DSC measure-

ment; this can be explained by a slight squeezing of the polymer during the forming process. Local fibre volume content can vary due to unequal pressure distribution and uneven squeezing of polymer melt. A fibre volume content of 53 % at a core layer thickness of approx. 300 μm was determined here. On the other hand, the adhesion agent used prevented an unambiguous determination of the crystallinity, since the adhesive agent adhered to the polyamide. A clear determination by DSC measurement was therefore impossible. Preliminary trials without an adhesion agent showed that the crystallinity at 80 °C cooling cycle temperature is approx. 22-24 % and without cooling approx. 30-33 % for pure polyamide. Similar results obtained with the organosheet whereby the resulting crystallinity obtained higher than the measurements in the DSC. An explanation for the higher crystallinity is probably the large contact area with the metallic surface layer which can serve as a nucleating agent. This is also indicated by the measured values, but a statistical verification is not possible yet. For further investigations, a theoretical crystallinity calculated from the cooling curve and the measurements of the DSC were used as an assistant, see Table 2. Therefore, the average cooling rate in the range of 170-200 °C was considered. The crystallinity was calculated based on the resulting cooling rate. From this crystallinity the temperature range is adjusted and the average cooling rate in the adjusted range is estimated. This cooling rate is used to determine a new crystallinity as shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8: Calculation of the theoretical crystallinity

Number	Sample	Tool temperature cold cycle in °C	Cooling rate in the recrystallization range in K/min	Theoretical crystallinity in %
1	Organosheet	80	-34.13	26.1
2	Organosheet	80	-33.19	26.1
3	Organosheet	80	-31.31	26.2
4	Organosheet	100	-28.31	26.4
5	Organosheet	50	-38.44	25.8
6	Organosheet	1*	-3.94	27.9
7	Polyamide	80	-29.6	24.7
8	Polyamide	80	-29.6	24.7
9	Polyamide	80	-32.6	24.3
10	Polyamide	2*	-13.7	26.5
11	Polyamide	100	-32.8	24.3
12	Polyamide	50	-37.7	23.8
13	Polyamide	1*	-3.9	27.6

1* No active cooling, 2* Cooling down the hot cycle

Table 2: Cooling rate in the range of recrystallization

3.2 Temperature profile

Figure 9 and Figure 10 describe the temperature profile in the mould within the range of 100-220 °C. A very similar pattern can be observed in the samples with standard configurations 1-3 (Figure 9) and 7-9 (Figure 10). The decrease of the cooling cycle temperature (samples 5, 12) leads - as expected - to a faster cooling. In addition, the increase of the cold cycle temperature (samples 4, 11) leads to a reduction of the cooling time. Moreover, it shows that the variation of the cooling cycle temperature from 80 °C to 50 °C or 100 °C has only a negligible influence on the first few minutes of cooling and thus on the assumed recrystallization process. However, the situation is different in the experiments without cooling (samples 6, 13) and in the experiments with cooling the hot oil cycle. (sample 10).

Figure 9: Temperature profile organosheet

Figure 10: Temperature profile polyamide

3.3 Mechanical tests

The mechanical examination focused on four-point bending based on DIN EN ISO 14125 and lap shear tests described in 2.2, Sample preparation. The four-point bending results are described in Figure 11.

Figure 11: Four-point bending, overview

Figure 11 demonstrates a similar pattern for the two series. Significant differences between the samples with different cooling temperature with or without fibre-reinforcement are not noticeable neither in the individual measurement series nor between series. Considering the results in more detail, Figure 12 illustrates the flexural modulus of the samples. Neither for the test series with organosheet nor for the test series with polyamide foil an exact statement can be made. The high standard deviation in the measurement series shows only tendencies, although these do not seem to be clear either. An increase of the modulus with slower cooling due to an increase of the crystallinity was expected; this cannot be confirmed.

Figure 12: Flexural modulus at different temperatures

Figure 13 illustrates a comparison between the maximum bending stress for different cooling temperatures. The situation for polyamide looks similar to the comparison of flexural modulus in Figure 12. The standard deviation obscures the possible effects and no tendencies can be detected. The situation is quite different for the fibre-reinforced polyamide samples. A decreasing course can be observed with higher cooling temperatures of the cold oil cycle, leading to a higher crystallinity of the samples. The influence of the cooling rate could be of more significance in the samples with glass fibre-

reinforcements, since on the one hand the fibre serves as the nucleus for crystallization. On the other hand the connection, i.e. the contact surface and thus the force transmission of the polymer to the glass fibre, is increased additionally. A change in the crystallinity of the adhesive agent which based on a copolymer should be kept in mind. Furthermore, it was observed that almost all samples with organosheet failed by delamination during the test.

Figure 13: Maximum bending stress

Equations 1-3 show the influence of the monomaterials on the flexural modulus of the sandwiches. This modulus was calculated using the rule of mixtures, shown by [7] to be an appropriate value for calculation properties of sandwiches. As characteristic values, a Young's modulus of 210 GPa was assumed for the steel used, 2 GPa for the polyamide and 80 GPa for the fibre. By multiplying with the volume fraction, the proportion of the respective monomaterials was calculated. Equation 4 shows the sum of the individual materials. This fits very well with the measured values in Figure 12, but also shows that the matrix influence with 0.3 GPa is very favourable. In relation to this, the combination of fibre and matrix with 14.4 GPa has a much greater influence.

$$210 \text{ GPa} * 0,67 = 140 \text{ GPa} \quad (1)$$

$$2 \text{ GPa} * 0,16 = 0,3 \text{ GPa} \quad (2)$$

$$80 \text{ GPa} * 0,18 = 14,1 \text{ GPa} \quad (3)$$

$$140 \text{ GPa} + 0,3 \text{ GPa} + 14,1 \text{ GPa} = 154,4 \text{ GPa} \quad (4)$$

The lap shear test demonstrates a similar behaviour for the organosheet as shown in Figure 14. A reduced cooling rate causes less adhesion. Furthermore, the adhesion of the fibre-reinforced samples is clearly worse than the adhesion of the samples without reinforcement. This is due to the compacting of the core material. The amount of polymer squeezed out so that there is insufficient matrix between the fibre and the metal surface seen in Figure 15 a). Nevertheless, a pattern can be recognized with equal compression. Comparing the polyamide measuring series, no progressions can be detected. On the one hand, an increase of the shear strength at a cooling cycle temperature of 50-80 °C seems to be recognizable. On the other hand, this trend does not seem to be continued in the tests without cooling and with cooling of the hot cycle.

Figure 14: Lap shear tests

Investigations on the fracture surface showed a predominantly cohesive failure of the bonding agent, see Figure 15 a). The fracture in the adhesive agent occurs in 77% of the samples of the organosheet, in the other cases a mixed fraction appeared, see Figure 15 b). In the measurement series with polyamide, the most frequent failure behaviour was also fracture in the adhesive agent with 71%. Second most frequent fracture behaviour was a mixture failure in combination with a polymer fracture as shown in Figure 15 c). Figures 15 e) and f) show the polymer side (e) and the metal side of image d) enlarged. The slightly yellowish colour is due to the adhesion agent, which adheres to both sides and is therefore showing cohesive failure in the adhesion agent.

Figure 15: Fracture images Lap shear tests

5 CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, the change in the cold cycle temperature, i.e. the cooling rate, causes a slight change in the mechanical properties. Especially at the beginning of cooling, a change in the cold cycle temperature only has a minor effect in the investigated area; this effect can be seen more clearly by changing the cooling rate of the hot cycle or in experiments without cooling.

A four-point bending characterization proved not to be very effective, as the laminates investigated had a too thin core layer. The results of the lap shear experiments showed that a decrease of the cooling rate causes a weakening of the bond in the samples with organosheet as core layer. In the samples with a core layer of polyamide, no clear effect could be stated. The assumption that an increase of the amorphous fraction favors the interface bonding was already indicated in [8]. This could only be confirmed with the organosheets.

In order to optimize the adhesion of the organosheet material and to gain similarly high lap shear strengths as in the investigated polyamide, an optimization of the layer structure should be performed. An additional layer of polyamide inserted between the metallic layer and the fiber-reinforced core is suggested. Furthermore, more than 70% of the cohesive failure occurred in the adhesion agent.

It should be noted that this is based on a copolyamide and can therefore be influenced by a change in the cooling rate as well. In addition, the investigations showed that the recrystallization temperature of the investigated materials shifted to a not insignificant extent.

6 OUTLOOK

Next steps should be monitoring the entire U-section and investigating how the bending angle in the profile affects the properties of the core layer. For future investigations, the effect of the cooling circuit temperature on thicker core layers will be investigated. Special interest will be given to the formation of the crystalline structure and the dependence on crystallization nucleus such as the metallic surface or the fibre-reinforcement. In addition, an enlargement of the core layer should have an effect on further bending investigations of the sandwich component. In this context, it is also interesting to install local reinforcements in the process in order to design it load-optimized. Further investigations will be carried out in order to improve the adhesion.

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